

Task Scheduling Library for Optimising Time-Scale Molecular Dynamics Simulations

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Abstract

In the particular use case for the mini-project described here, E-CAM is interested in the challenge of bridging timescales. To study molecular dynamics with atomistic detail, timesteps must be used on the order of a femto-second. Many problems in biological chemistry, materials science, and other fields involve events that only spontaneously occur after a millisecond or longer (for example, biomolecular conformational changes, or nucleation processes). That means that around 10^{12} time steps would be needed to see a single millisecond-scale event. This is the problem of „rare events” in theoretical and computational chemistry. Modern supercomputers are beginning to make it possible to obtain trajectories long enough to observe some of these processes, but to fully characterize a transition with proper statistics, many examples are needed. In order to obtain many examples the same application must be run many thousands of times with varying inputs. To manage this kind of computation, task scheduling library is needed. The main elements of the mentioned scheduling library are: task definition, a task scheduling (handled in Python) and task execution (facilitated by the MPI layer). While traditionally an HTC workload is looked down upon in the HPC space, the scientific use case for extreme-scale resources exists and algorithms that require a coordinated approach make efficient libraries that implement this approach increasingly important in the HPC space. The 5 Petaflop booster technology of JURECA is an interesting concept with respect to this approach since the offloading approach of heavy computation marries perfectly to the concept outlined here.

1. Introduction

The initial motivation for this library is driven by the ensemble-type calculations that are required in many scientific fields, and in particular in the materials science domain in which the E-CAM Centre of Excellence operates. The scope for parallelisation is best contextualised by the Dask documentation [2]:

A common approach to parallel execution in user-space is task scheduling. In task scheduling we break our program into many medium-sized tasks or units of computation, often a function call on a non-trivial amount of data. We represent these tasks as nodes in a graph with edges between nodes if one task depends on data produced by another. We call upon a task scheduler to execute this graph in a way that respects these data dependencies and leverages parallelism where possible, multiple independent tasks can be run simultaneously.

Many solutions exist. This is a common approach in parallel execution frameworks. Often task scheduling logic hides within other larger frameworks (Luigi, Storm, Spark, IPython Parallel, and so on) and so is often reinvented.

Dask is a specification that encodes task schedules with minimal incidental complexity using terms common to all Python projects, namely dicts, tuples, and callables. Ideally this minimum solution is easy to adopt and understand by a broad community.

While we were attracted by this approach, Dask did not support *task-level* parallelisation (in particular multi-node tasks). We researched other options (including Celery, PyCOMPSs, IPyParallel and others) and organised a workshop that explored some of these (see <https://www.cecac.org/workshop-0-1650.html> for further details).

The initial idea for the implementation of this project was to use `MPI.Comm.spawn`, which is a collective call and spawns a child MPI job with n processes from within an MPI task. The problem with this is that, while part of the MPI standard, the implementation of this is highly specific to the MPI implementation itself, with a

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considerable amount of configuration information hidden (and often undocumented) in the `MPI_Info` argument to this call. This information is not part of the standard which means that the approach is highly non-portable, potentially requiring source code edits on all platforms where it is used. Not only this, but it was also our experience that, given its relative obscurity, it is not actually implemented at all in some cases (since it requires coupling to the resource manager, of which there are many possibilities).

Ultimately, once we came to discover the existence of the Dask extension `dask_jobqueue`, we realised that it would be possible for us to build upon its functionality to include support for parallel task workloads without having to resort to such *exotic* MPI functionality.

The approach described in the rest of this document allows for multi-level parallelisation (at the task level and at the framework level) while leveraging all the pre-existing effort within the Dask framework (such as scheduling, resilience, data management and resource scaling).

The resulting library is flexible, scalable, efficient and adaptive. It is capable of simultaneously utilising CPUs, KNL and GPUs and dynamically adjusting its use of these resources based on the resource requirements of the scheduled task workload. The ultimate scalability and hardware capabilities of the solution is dictated by the scalability characteristics of the tasks themselves (if there are 100 nodes per task with GPUs, then the library can carry out N of these at once depending on resource availability).

1.1. Scientific Use Case

Across scientific fields, High Throughput Computing (or HTC) is becoming a necessary approach in order to fully utilize next-generation computer hardware. As an example, consider molecular dynamics: Excellent work over the years has developed software that can simulate a single trajectory very efficiently using massive parallelization. Unfortunately, for a fixed number of atoms, the extent of possible parallelization is limited. However, many methods, including semiclassical approaches to quantum dynamics and some approaches to rare events, require running thousands of independent molecular dynamics trajectories. Intelligent HTC, which can treat each trajectory as a task and manage data dependencies between tasks, provides a way to run these simulations on hardware up to the exascale, thus opening the possibility of studying previously intractable systems.

The range of use for intelligent HTC in scientific programs is broad. For example, intelligent HTC can be used to select and run many single-point electronic structure calculations in order to develop approximate potential energy surfaces. Even more examples can be found in the wide range of methods that require many trajectories, where each trajectory can be treated as a task, such as:

- rare events methods, like transition interface sampling, weighted ensemble, committor analysis, and variants of the Bennett-Chandler reactive flux method;
- semi-classical methods, including the phase integration method and the semi-classical initial value representation;
- adaptive sampling methods for Markov state model generation;
- approaches such as nested sampling, which use many short trajectories to estimate partition functions.

The challenge is that most developers of scientific software are not familiar with the way such packages can simplify their development process, and the packages that exist may not scale to exascale. The library described here is intended to provide an opportunity for scientific developers to add support for HTC to their codes.

2. Task scheduling library

The provided library is written in Python programming language [7] as an additional feature for `dask_jobqueue` [4] which in turn utilizes the Dask library [2]. The former is targeted for deploying the latter on several job queuing systems, such as Slurm [8] or PBS [1] with the use of a Python programming interface. The main enhancements of basic `dask_jobqueue` functionality is the introduction of an extended and more hidden configuration process which allows the end-user to create parallelized tasks in a convenient way without knowledge of implementation details (e.g., resource manager or MPI launcher). Such distinction of configuration details provides an easy to use environment but also allows for customisation of functionality if necessary. The core idea is to pre-configure every needed setting for successfully scattering a computation across nodes for users which results in minimal input from their side in code customisation for execution on clusters. Since the JURECA cluster (see Section 3.1.) is using the Slurm queuing system, the discussed library is mainly aimed for this workload manager (with possibility of extending configurations for other systems supported by `dask_jobqueue`). The default configurations are suited for several node partitions types such as GPU nodes (`gpus`, `vis`), KNL ones (`kn1`), high memory nodes (`mem256`, `mem512`, `mem1024`) or regular CUPs-based nodes (`batch`, `devel`). Those default adjustments are set in a configuration file which can be modified in twofold ways, i.e. by manual user changes to the configuration or by overriding them in the code implementation process.

Another feature provided by the subject library is a set of Python decorators for the library. Such an approach separates the inner implementation of batch scripts creation and communication with Slurm system from user side code declaration. Main decorators are `on_cluster` and `task`. The former provides cluster computation support and the latter indicates that a given function shall be executed on cluster nodes. In many scenarios inserting those two decorators in user's code is enough for transition from plain Python code into a distributed computation.

The library also supports MPI-based computation to distribute tasks over nodes of cluster. This is provided by the `mpi_task` decorator. It enables combining Python-level code parallelization with external MPI-level scripts execution.

2.1. Implementation details

The library implementation is written in Python and is available at https://github.com/E-CAM/jobqueue_features. The main structure is focused on several classes which interconnect between themselves resulting in the overall logical structure. This section describes most important elements of the library.

2.1.1. Configuration file

The configuration file is written in a generic way (in YAML [6] syntax), following the style already present in `dask_jobqueue`. It has been significantly expanded to account for:

- system architecture;
- how MPI programs are launched;
- configuring for MPI and MPI/OpenMP tasks;
- configuring for accessing resources with specific hardware characteristics (`queue-type`).

Default settings for resources on JURECA are distributed in the default configuration file. This file stores all necessary settings to execute code on all resources types without the need for adding any (additional) resource manager parameters. An example of configuration is presented in Listing 1.

```
...
jobqueue-features:
  scheduler: slurm

slurm:
  default-queue-type: batch          # default queue_type to use
  cores-per-node: 24                # Physical cores per node
  hyperthreading-factor: 2          # hyperthreading factor available
  minimum-cores: 24                 # Minimum number of cores per dask worker is 1 full node
  gpu-job-extra: []                 # Only relevant for particular queue_type
  warning: null

# MPI/OpenMP related settings ----
mpi-mode: False                     # MPI mode is off by default
mpi-launcher: srun                   # Default launcher for MPI app (unused unless in MPI mode)
nodes: null                           # Default node allocation (unused unless in MPI mode)
ntasks-per-node: 24                 # Default tasks per node (unused unless in MPI mode)
# cpus-per-task: 1                  # Default cpus per task (unused unless in MPI mode)
openmp-env-extra: ['export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${SLURM_CPUS_PER_TASK}',
                  'export OMP_PROC_BIND=spread',
                  'export OMP_PLACES=threads']
...

```

Listing 1. Example part of the default YAML configuration file

2.1.2. Cluster controller

The next crucial part is the `ClusterController` class whose instance is created once at the beginning of execution (singleton pattern) and is available across all other components. The Controller keeps a collection of clusters and clients so it can provide these via decorators to submitted tasks by injecting the cluster's ID or by returning the default cluster. See Listing 2 for the shortened interface.

```
class ClusterController(object):
    def __init__(self): ...

    def get_cluster(self, id_=None): ...

    def add_cluster(self, id_=None, cluster=None): ...

    def _make_cluster(self, id_, cluster=None): ...

    def _close(self): ...

    ...

clusters_controller_singleton = ClusterController()

```

Listing 2. Interface of `ClusterController` class

2.1.3. Cluster

The end cluster class for which the library works is a `CustomSLURMCluster` which derives from `CustomClusterMixin` (an internal class) and `SLURMCluster` (from the `dask_jobqueue` library). Its interface is shown on Listing 3. It mainly merges logic from the reading of settings from configurations file (`CustomClusterMixin`) and setting a cluster itself (`SLURMCluster`).

```
class CustomSLURMCluster(CustomClusterMixin, SLURMCluster):
    def __init__(self, **kwargs): ...

    def _update_script_nodes(self): ...
```

Listing 3. Interface of `CustomSLURMCluster` class

2.1.4. Decorators

In this library there exist the following decorators: `on_cluster`, `task` and `mpi_task`. The `on_cluster` gets or creates clusters from cluster controller. If no id is explicitly provided, the controller provides the default cluster (`LocalCluster` from Dask distributed library). At initialization it also manages the required number of nodes and ensures successful resource allocation by submitting jobs to the resource manager. The `task` decorator gets a client from cluster controller and submits a wrapped function to the given cluster to compute. The `mpi_task` decorator derives from `task` and enhances it with MPI specific settings (e.g. the MPI launcher type). For shortened interface see the Listing 4.

```
class on_cluster(object):
    def __init__(self, cluster_id=None, cluster=None, scale=None): ...

    def __call__(self, f): ...

class task(object):
    def __init__(self, cluster_id=None): ...

    def __call__(self, f): ...

    def _get_cluster_and_client(self): ...

    def _submit(self, cluster, client, f, *args, **kwargs): ...

class mpi_task(task):
    def __init__(self, cluster_id=None, default_mpi_tasks=1): ...

    def _submit(self, cluster, client, f, *args, **kwargs): ...
```

Listing 4. Interfaces of decorator classes

2.1.5. Example

Listing 5 shows a minimal example which uses `task` and `on_cluster` decorators. As can be seen, the end-user is not forced to into any additional actions beside decorating the source code functions. The configuration, communication and serialization is isolated and hidden from user code which results in an ease of usage. For setting cluster the `set_default_cluster` function was used.

```
from jobqueue_features import task, set_default_cluster, on_cluster
from jobqueue_features.clusters import CustomSLURMCluster

set_default_cluster(CustomSLURMCluster)

@task()
def square(x):
    return x ** 2

@on_cluster()
def main():
    sq_tasks = list(map(square, range(1, 100)))
    print([t.result() for t in sq_tasks])

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()
```

Listing 5. Example of decorators usage for parallelizing computation

3. Experiments and results

3.1. Testing environment

The primary testing resource has been JURECA, which is a petaflop-scale modular supercomputer operated by Jülich Supercomputing Centre at Forschungszentrum Jülich [5]. The system combines a flexible Cluster module with a scalability focused Booster module (based on the Xeon Phi many-core processor) in addition to a GPU-accelerated partition. With its novel architecture, it supports a wide variety of high-performance computing and data analytics workloads.

The software stack required to support the library development, including the system-wide provision of the library itself, has been done via EasyBuild [3] (which is a software build and installation framework that allows the management of scientific software on HPC systems in an efficient way). See <https://github.com/easybuilders/JSC/pull/6> for more details on specifications of the supporting software stack.

3.2. Experiments

The development of the library had two major aspects, one that targeted a simplified user experience (minimising configuration and implementation overhead for the end user) and the other that targeted leveraging the hardware heterogeneity of a resource such as JURECA. For the first case, it was possible to integrate a test suite directly into the library. The second case requires the specific configuration of the computing resource and are included as examples (and could be considered as regression tests for the particular resource).

With respect to the library itself, in the subsections below, we include specific experiments that highlight the overhead incurred through the library and also the scalability and flexibility of the solution.

3.2.1. Initial Evaluation

The initial questions we wished to address with our library were three-fold:

- Does it work? (obvious but essential)
- How easy is it to integrate?
- What is the overhead?

The answer to the first question is quite non-trivial. For a particular task, you may require a particular hardware environment and a particular software stack. The caveat with respect to the hardware environment is that you need to be able to have a network that supports TCP connections between the scheduler and the *workers* (which process and execute the tasks that are queued). For CPU and GPU tasks, the scheduler can be run from a login node and the connections made via IPoIB to the workers. For KNL tasks there is a complication in that there is no direct IP connection between the KNL nodes and the login nodes (on JURECA). This requires that KNL workers can only be started from within the batch environment, where such a connection does exist. It is possible for us to support this via a cluster-in-cluster approach, but we would have much preferred to handle all workers from the login nodes.

With respect to the software stack, this is a more global problem but again is highlighted by the KNL booster. On the booster, you have a different micro-architecture and you need to completely change your software stack to support this. The design of the software stack implementation on JURECA simplifies this but ensuring your tasks are run in the correct software environment is one of the more difficult things to get right in the library. To illustrate this complexity, we reproduce some of the configuration from one of our examples in Listings 6-8.

```
GROMACS_cluster = CustomSLURMCluster(  
    name='GROMACS_cluster', walltime='00:15:00', nodes=2, mpi_mode=True, maximum_scale=10,  
    env_extra=[  
        'module --force purge',  
        'module use /usr/local/software/jureca/OtherStages',  
        'module load Stages/Devel-2018b',  
        'module load Intel/2019.0.117-GCC-7.3.0',  
        'module load ParaStationMPI/5.2.1-1',  
        'module load GROMACS/2018.3',  
        'module load Dask/Nov2018Bundle-Python-2.7.15',  
    ]  
)
```

Listing 6. Example class instances for CPU cluster on JURECA

```
GROMACS_gpu_cluster = CustomSLURMCluster(  
    name='GROMACS_gpu_cluster', walltime='00:15:00', nodes=2, mpi_mode=True,  
    queue_type='gpus', maximum_scale=5,  
    env_extra=[  
        'module --force purge',  
        'module use /usr/local/software/jureca/OtherStages',  
        'module load Stages/Devel-2018b',  
        'module load Intel/2019.0.117-GCC-7.3.0',  
        'module load ParaStationMPI/5.2.1-1',  
    ]  
)
```

```

    'module load GROMACS/2018.3',
    'module load Dask/Nov2018Bundle-Python-2.7.15',
]
)

```

Listing 7. Example class instances for GPU cluster on JURECA

```

GROMACS_knl_cluster = CustomSLURMCluster(
    name='GROMACS_knl_cluster', walltime='00:15:00', nodes=4, mpi_mode=True,
    maximum_scale=10, queue_type='knl', python='python',
    env_extra=[
        'module --force purge',
        'unset SOFTWAREROOT',
        'module use /usr/local/software/jurecabooster/OtherStages',
        'module load Stages/Devel-2018b',
        'module load Intel/2019.0.117-GCC-7.3.0',
        'module load IntelMPI/2019.0.117', # MUST use IntelMPI (don't know why yet)
        'module load GROMACS/2018.3',
        'module load Dask/Nov2018Bundle-Python-2.7.15',
    ]
)

```

Listing 8. Example class instances for KNL cluster on JURECA

These configurations also lead us to our second point on ease of integration. What is interesting to note is that while the configuration of the *clusters* (which define the template required to submit workers to the appropriate queue of the resource manager) as shown is quite non-trivial, it can be located within a single file which will need to be tuned for the particular resource. With respect to the tasks themselves, no tuning is necessarily required. Take for example a task derived from one of these definitions, which can be seen in Listing 9. There is nothing in this task that depends on the particular system where it is run, the system dependencies are entirely handled by the (site-wide) configuration of the library and the (user-specific) configuration of the the clusters required. One can integrate a decision mechanism in the application to allow for the availability (or not) of each of the cluster type.

```

@on_cluster(cluster=GROMACS_cluster, cluster_id='GROMACS_cluster')
@mpi_task(cluster_id='GROMACS_cluster')
def run_mpi(**kwargs):
    script_path = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), 'resources', 'helloworld2.py')
    t = mpi_wrap(pre_launcher_opts='time -f "%e"', executable='python', exec_args=script_path,
                **kwargs)
    return t

```

Listing 9. Example task based on cluster from Listing 6

3.2.2. Scalability and Overhead

Each worker is an individual job on the system, and individually queued, so the availability of workers is determined by the queuing system, not by the application (which only makes the request for additional workers). In this scenario, weak scaling has no real meaning since we cannot guarantee all workers are allocated at once (and one of the strengths of the library is exactly this flexibility).

Fig. 1. Overhead of the framework per task in seconds for various numbers of tasks and on various architectures. Total number of tasks is given on the X-axis, with the maximum number of workers available being 10 (for each architecture).

The allocation of tasks to workers is dynamic based on worker availability, so the number of tasks per worker is not strictly fixed (but is expected to be roughly equal to the number of tasks divided by the number of workers,

$\frac{N_{tasks}}{N_{workers}}$). If we assume the tasks per worker is indeed given by $\frac{N_{tasks}}{N_{workers}}$ (which is likely to be roughly true), since the workers are independent we are really only interested in the N_{tasks} per worker to investigate strong scalability, i.e., strong scalability means less tasks per worker (since there would be more workers available to process a given set of tasks). This trend can be extracted from Fig. 1 (where $N_{workers}$ is ~ 10 so to get tasks per worker, simply divide the X-axis by 10). What we essentially see is that less tasks per worker means higher overhead per task. There are a few simplifications and assumptions in this analysis though that are better explained if we focus simply on the *overhead* introduced by the library.

What we are interested in measuring is the ability of the library to handle an increasing number of tasks per worker, and highlighting how the total overhead is small and the total overhead per task drops as the task count increases. It is not so easy to get this in a pure form due to the fact that the primary source of overhead comes from starting workers. A significant proportion of this overhead is in turn due to the time to configure the nodes for a job within the cluster (which is a system overhead, completely independent of the library). An estimate of the system configuration overhead for the various architectures on JURECA is provided in Table 1.

	Haswell	KNL	GPU
Configuration time (per job, in seconds)	10	24	8

Table 1. System configuration time per job on each of the hardware types available on JURECA

If we use a simple `Hello world!` program, we can directly measure the overhead of the library and use data from the resource manager to account for the system overhead. There are a number of ways one can attempt to visualise this, here we chose two: the overhead per task, in Fig. 1, and the total overhead of the framework in seconds, in Fig. 2. For each case, there are 2 nodes per worker (68 cores on a KNL node, 4 GPUs on a GPU node and 24 physical cores on a CPU node), with 10 workers each (so, at peak utilisation, a total of 480 CPUs, 1360 KNL cores and 80 GPUs). The total overhead of the framework was calculated as:

$$T_{overhead} = T_{wall} - T_{task} - (T_{config}N_{workers}),$$

where:

- T_{wall} – total walltime reported by the resource manager for all jobs related to the task set;
- T_{task} – total combined runtime of all tasks;
- T_{config} – average resource configuration time for each job;
- $N_{workers}$ – number of workers started for the task set (i.e., number of jobs submitted to the resource manager).

Fig. 2. Total overhead of the framework in seconds for various numbers of tasks and on various architectures.

The interesting point to note for Fig. 2 is that the total overhead is relatively static over time until we get to larger task counts. The sudden increase at 2000 tasks for the KNL data is mostly due to the fact that the simulation took long enough that our workers began to exceed their allowed walltimes, resulting in the resilience mechanism being utilised and additional workers being started.

The overall message is that overhead is very small, particularly if we look at it per task as in Fig. 1. At higher task counts we are seeing almost 90% throughput efficiency for trivial tasks, if the tasks executed for any reasonable length of time this throughput would be much higher.

While simplistic, it is informative to compare, given Table 1, what are the savings as compared to running the tasks directly through the resource manager. This can be seen in Table 2. A final remark is to note that these savings scale according to the resources used by the task (i.e, the savings scale linearly with respect to the resources used by the task).

Tasks	Haswell	KNL	GPU
10	33.19	-93.61	-48.8
50	357.99	441.55	297.58
100	871.84	1759.37	657.45
200	1860.38	4160.43	1423.28
500	4836.35	11321.85	3827.79
1000	9796.77	23327.39	7824.52
2000	19784.67	46548.92	15803.22

Table 2. Time savings (in seconds) of running tasks through the library rather than through the resource manager

3.2.3. LAMMPS as a task

LAMMPS is one of the molecular dynamics engines that can be used by OPS but is also an application that is used heavily by others in the E-CAM community. As such we have also used the developed library as a show case for how it might be integrated with another E-CAM software project (see https://gitlab.e-cam2020.eu/e-cam/E-CAM-Library/merge_requests/65 for more detailed context).

The Lmod module tool used on JURECA has the ability to store a set of modules to provide a particular environment, using `module save ...`, which can be restored with `module restore ...`, simplifying the long list of required modules. An example of this use is shown in Listing 10. Note the careful selection of `ntasks_per_node=2` and `cpus_per_task=12`, which are optimal choices for LAMMPS tasks in this use case.

```
lammps_cluster = CustomSLURMCluster(
    name='lammps_cluster', walltime='00:40:00', nodes=2, ntasks_per_node=2, cpus_per_task=12,
    mpi_mode=True, maximum_scale=10,
    env_extra=[
        'module --force purge',
        'module use /usr/local/software/jureca/OtherStages',
        'module restore picore',
    ]
)
```

Listing 10. Cluster configuration for LAMMPS using Lmod module sets

The performance characteristics of LAMMPS are set by command line arguments. This makes executing tasks efficiently on any of the architectures very straightforward: you ensure you have the correct software environment for the task and that you execute with the correct performance flags. This is illustrated in Listing 11.

```
# The generic lammps execution
def run_lammps(performance_args='', **kwargs):
    standard_exec_args = '-in templatev5_nokspace-scaling.in -var Replicate_nx 6 \' \
        -var Replicate_ny 8 -var Replicate_nz 4 -var SAMPLE_frequency 2000'
    exec_args = performance_args + standard_exec_args
    return mpi_wrap(executable='lmp', exec_args=exec_args, **kwargs)

@on_cluster(cluster=lammps_gpu_cluster, cluster_id='lammps_gpu_cluster', scale=10)
@mpi_task(cluster_id='lammps_gpu_cluster')
def run_mpi_gpu(**kwargs):
    t = run_lammps(performance_args='-k on g 2 -sf kk -pk kokkos gpu/direct off',
        **kwargs)
    return t

@on_cluster(cluster=lammps_knl_cluster, cluster_id='lammps_knl_cluster', scale=10)
@mpi_task(cluster_id='lammps_knl_cluster')
def run_mpi_knl(**kwargs):
    t = run_lammps(performance_args="-sf omp -pk omp {}".format(os.getenv("OMP_NUM_THREADS")),
        **kwargs)
    return t

@on_cluster(cluster=lammps_cluster, cluster_id='lammps_cluster', scale=10)
@mpi_task(cluster_id='lammps_cluster')
def run_mpi(**kwargs):
    t = run_lammps(performance_args="-sf omp -pk omp {}".format(os.getenv("OMP_NUM_THREADS")),
        **kwargs)
    return t
```

Listing 11. Configuring LAMMPS tasks to run on 3 different architectures

3.2.4. *OpenPathSampling committor analysis as a task*

Committor analysis is a powerful, but computationally expensive, tool to study reaction mechanisms in complex systems. For a committor simulation, configuration space is divided into a reactant region, a product region, and the transition region. The reactant and product regions are stable states defined as "core sets," where a trajectory launched near one state is extremely likely to return to that state before visiting the other state.

The committor for a given configuration is defined as the probability that a trajectory launched from that point reaches the product state before the reactant state. This can be determined by running many trajectories from the initial configuration with different initial velocities, and stopping them as soon as they enter one of the two states. This problem is highly parallelizable, however, the duration of each trajectory cannot be known in advance. Therefore load balancing can be difficult, and approaches such as the one presented here are well-suited to this problem.

The committor simulation can grow in two directions: more initial configurations will provide a more complete exploration of the transition region, and more trajectories per initial configuration will provide better accuracy. In previous work, the computational cost of the committor simulation has led to limitations in both directions — this is a problem where very large computational resources could be put to use.

We developed a tool based on the OpenPathSampling (OPS) committor analysis to perform the committor in parallel. Each task is the committor for a single initial snapshot. Due to existing challenges in serialization of some OPS objects, we use a filesystem-based approach to send the tasks to the workers.

4. Conclusions

The library in it's current form achieves it's original goals:

- it is efficient and scalable, handling thousands of tasks with minimal overhead;
- it is resilient;
- it can handle tasks that execute on multiple architectures and multiple nodes;
- it simplifies the interface to the underlying libraries (most useful in our particular use cases);
- extreme scalability would result from combining this library with tasks of moderate scalability but with a high task count.

One of the key challenges is configuring the right software environment for the tasks to run, which is particularly acute when dealing with distinct micro-architectures. This is handled via EasyBuild and the software installation mechanisms available on JURECA.

There is, unsurprisingly, room for further improvement and development. In particular, the MPI implementation at present only forks an MPI process, the interaction with this tasks can currently only happen via processing STDOUT/STDERR or through the file system. The design for how the Python interface of an MPI enabled application could be leveraged is already clear but there was insufficient time to implement this. A conceptual proof of principle for this can be seen in Listing 12. The implementation of this is likely very important for more complex use cases.

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
"""
Parallel Hello World
"""

from mpi4py import MPI
import os
import dill

comm = MPI.COMM_WORLD
size = comm.Get_size()
rank = comm.Get_rank()
name = MPI.Get_processor_name()
all_nodes = comm.gather(name, root=0)
if rank == 0:
    # This is the task, which is only defined on root
    def identity(n):
        import time
        time.sleep(2)
        return n

    id2 = dill.dumps(identity)
    all_nodes = set(all_nodes)
    print("Running %d tasks on nodes %s." % (size, all_nodes))
else:
    id2 = None
id1 = dill.loads(comm.bcast(id2, root=0))
print(id1(rank))
MPI.Finalize()
```

Listing 12. Proof of principle for creating tasks with a Python interface

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